
A Lesson in Politics: Some Remarks on Leo Strauss' Socrates and Aristophanes*

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Abstract: In the first paragraph of this paper, I tackle the problem represented by Leo Strauss' work on Aristophanes' comedies *Socrates and Aristophanes*. In the second and third part, I analyze the character of Socrates' atheism, and the influence of natural science on his unbelief. The fourth part addresses the tension between the fundamental requirements of the city and the requirements of the philosophical way of life. The final section dwells on the peculiar meaning of Aristophanes' political lesson.

Keywords: Leo Strauss, Aristophanes, Socrates, political philosophy, poetry

1. Leo Strauss' "real work"

To my knowledge, the philosopher who stated the case for poetry more forcefully than anyone else during the last two centuries was Friedrich Nietzsche in the *Birth of Tragedy*. In a sense, he once again opened the ancient quarrel between poetry and philosophy, or poetry and science¹. His recovery of poetry was related to a sort of political action or spiritual warfare², and this should be of no surprise, since even the classical quarrel between poetry and philosophy was of political significance. Leo Strauss' *Socrates and Aristophanes* faces the same issue, apparently taking the side of poetry. We can ask what Strauss' intention might have been, and as a preliminary hypothesis I would assume that he was working on a renewal of political philosophy³; but for now it seems better, following his advice, to start from the surface.

Socrates and Aristophanes is a truly unique book⁴. Firstly, it is the only book in which Strauss analyzes, one by one, all the works of a single author. Only *Thoughts on Machiavelli* is comparable, aside from the fact that it does not analyze all the works of Machiavelli one after the other, but is merely a close reading of the *Prince* and the *Discourses*. Secondly, *Socrates and Aristophanes* is a commentary on the works of a comic poet, not a commentary devoted to the work of a political philosopher. Nor is it even a commentary devoted to the work of a political historian, as in the case of the chapter on Thucydides in *The City and Man*. The title, however, points to two distinct figures: Socrates and Aristophanes. Socrates is the philosopher traditionally recognized as the originator of political philosophy and the philosopher who famously wrote nothing. In fact, we only ever deal with Socrates

through the writings of someone else: Plato's Socrates or Xenophon's Socrates. As in the case of *Xenophon's Socrates* or *Farabi's Plato*, one could speak of *Aristophanes' Socrates*, yet this is not how Strauss entitles his "real work"⁵. Why?

Strauss maintains that Aristophanes' comedy is the source to which we must turn in order to rediscover the pre-Socratic Socrates (pp. 4-6)⁶ who is simply a natural philosopher and not yet a sophisticated political philosopher (pp. 311-14). I am therefore tempted to say that the Socrates of *Socrates and Aristophanes* is neither the Socrates of Aristophanes nor the Socrates of, say, Xenophon. He is simply the unpolitical Socrates, that is, the unpolitical philosopher par excellence.

Now, why does Strauss need to recover the figure of the pre-Socratic Socrates? The reason for this is the crisis of the tradition of political philosophy⁷. This urgent need prompted Strauss to read *The Clouds* of Aristophanes, as we are told at the beginning of *Socrates and Aristophanes*. The crisis of our tradition forces us to return to its origins, to disinter its roots, to start over (p. 3). Our tradition vouches for the possibility and necessity of political philosophy, and in the nineteenth century our tradition was radically challenged. According to Strauss, the peak of this criticism is the attack of Nietzsche on Socrates and Plato: Nietzsche attacks the philosopher who, according to our tradition, founded political philosophy (pp. 6-8). The first, and perhaps the most important, formulation of Nietzsche's critique is developed in his first book, *The Birth of Tragedy*, where the German philosopher addresses some of the flaws which brought Aristophanes to his critique of the pre-Socratic Socrates. In *The Clouds*, Aristophanes subjects, so to speak, the pre-Socratic Socrates to a comic trial. In this comedy, the incredible limitations of the pre-Socratic Socrates are revealed: the first being his lack of prudence and self-knowledge; the second his inability to understand the needs of the city; the third his total misunderstanding of Eros (pp. 311-13).

Nietzsche takes up arguments similar to those of Aristophanes to use against Plato's Socrates: he criticizes the Platonic tradition of a Socratic, philosophical citizenship. But the traditional Socrates would seem to be completely free of the above-mentioned limitations: he is the champion of prudence and self-knowledge, the truly erotic man, the citizen par excellence, and the only real politician in Athens (p. 314)⁸. Nonetheless, this sort of citizen-philosopher, who is the emblem of our Great Tradition, has been violently and irreversibly challenged: from

Nietzsche's perspective, the very phenomenon of "Socrates" would actually be the most degenerated symptom of decadence, since the philosopher as such does not believe in the gods of the city, that is, he does not take political life seriously⁹.

But which point of view is adopted by Nietzsche in his critique of Socrates? Nietzsche adopts the perspective of the tragic vision of the world or of the tragic vision of human life, going back to the "first" Aeschylus:¹⁰ he adopts the perspective of a tragic poet. Aristophanes also stands for poetry, but he is a comedian. Both Aristophanes and Nietzsche, however, claim to be disciples of the god Dionysus (p. 22)¹¹. Two disciples of the god Dionysus attack the philosopher par excellence, Socrates: What is the difference between these two critics? How are we to determine which of the two is more radical? Of course, we are dealing with two profoundly different historical and political situations and, even more importantly, with the difference between the spirit of tragedy and the spirit of comedy. Only one thing seems to be certain: *The Clouds* provide us, as Allan Bloom claimed, with a "record, unparalleled in its detail and depth, of this first appearance of philosophy, and we can apprehend the natural, or at least primitive, responses to it, prior to philosophy's effect on the world. This provides a view of the beginning at a time when we may be witnessing the end, partly because we no longer know that beginning"¹².

2. Political responsibility and the philosophic way of life

Strauss starts, therefore, from the beginning and asks whether political philosophy is possible and necessary to begin with. He asks the question "why political philosophy?" We need to understand why Socrates brought philosophy down to the city and to the household (p. 4). One thing seems clear: in *The Clouds*, the philosopher receives both a political critique and a political lesson. This comedy, however, poses some questions that can only be answered by a careful reading of Aristophanes' other comedies (p. 53), and, in a sense, the purpose of *Socrates and Aristophanes* is the perfect understanding of Aristophanes' political critique of the philosophical way of life¹³.

What is the thrust of this criticism? It can be stated as follows: The philosopher does not take the city and its gods seriously. In other words, the philosopher lacks prudence because he questions what the city reveres as sacred (pp. 48-49) and, therefore, exposes himself to the moral indignation of his fellow citizens. The philosopher is in danger of being persecuted (and eventually of being prosecuted). Moreover, his teachings can be misinterpreted by corrupt men who may feel entitled to forget the precepts of morality and to act against them. For this reason, the philosopher may be perceived by good and upstanding citizens as an agent of disorder, as a threat to public order.

Socrates takes neither the city nor the conditions upon which social peace is based seriously – he ultimately fails to take the conditions for his own way of life seriously, which requires security and concentration. The *phrontisterion* is unable to secure its own political conditions of

possibility. The Socratic school corrupts young people and estranges them from their families and the city, but is materially dependent on it and on individual acts of generosity and petty theft. This community of natural scientists is exposed to the greatest danger when Socrates reveals the truth about the gods to Strepsiades. It is only Strepsiades' intellectual slowness that prevents him from being immediately aware that Socratic atheism destroys the main pillar of justice: in fact, if Zeus does not exist, then there is no guarantee that superhuman punishment awaits those who transgress the most fundamental of prohibitions (p. 19).

The prohibition of incest and the prohibition of patriicide are the fundamental pillars of political life or the life of every human community. Strauss defines these prohibitions (along with the need for divine worship) as unconditional requirements of the city (p. 304): these are the sacred restraints that underpin every closed or political society. But from the point of view of the pre-Socratic Socrates, Zeus, far from being a god, does not even exist (p. 19). Revealing the truth about the gods seems more urgent to him than respecting the basis of his fellow citizens' moral beliefs. For this reason, Aristophanes, as a poet who knows the limits and cravings of the human soul, comically chastises the philosopher for his superficiality.

When Strepsiades realizes the effects of Socratic education on his beloved and spoiled son Pheidippides, he is shocked and becomes angry: it is his moral indignation which literally brings down the Socratic school. We might say that the recommendation of the clouds to Strepsiades also applies to the philosopher: the new goddesses maintain that "the only thing that matters is the fear of the gods". Aristophanes seems to suggest that his friend Socrates publicly respect what is sacred to the city; he should, in a sense, pay lip service to the gods of the city. In this sense the poet tells Socrates to take the gods of the city seriously because, for good citizens, the only thing that matters is the fear of the gods (p. 44).

3. Socratic unbelief and the science of nature

But why does Socrates fail to take the gods of the city seriously? Why are natural science and the debunking of sacred things so closely related? As we know, Strauss writes that, for Socrates, "Zeus, far from being a god, does not even exist" (p. 19). This is the Straussian reading of *Clouds* v. 367 in which Socrates literally states: "What Zeus? Don't be silly. Zeus does not exist". From the philosophical point of view, belief in the existence of Zeus is equivalent to *leresis*, empty talk and nonsense. This is not so far from the spirit of Farabi, who defines divine promises of happiness in the afterlife as "ravings and old women's tales"¹⁴.

I think there are at least two reasons which may explain Socrates' unbelief. The first is as follows: Socrates does not take Zeus seriously firstly because Zeus is far from being a god (p. 33); but this would mean, at least, that Socrates knows what a god is. We are not offered any explicit definition here, but we know that, according to the poets, the gods are models of the blessed life. In a sense, Socrates seems to assume this basic tenet, but from

his philosophical point of view, Zeus cannot be a model of the blessed life, that is, a god, because of his childish indifference to learning (p. 33). Far from being a god, Zeus proves, indeed, to be a childish being. He is in actuality nothing but a proud and whimsical tyrant¹⁵. According to Strauss' Socrates, the model represented by Zeus does not live up to the ideal of a perfect being: the denial of the divinity of Zeus is implied by the assertion of the primacy of contemplative life¹⁶.

We cannot underestimate this statement; for, in order to deny the divinity of Zeus, it is not necessary at all to prove that Zeus does not exist. If Zeus were to exist, a wise man such as Socrates would not want to imitate him. The statement which indicates the childish character of Zeus completes the *elenchos* with which the Unjust Speech destroyed the Just Speech; Zeus is deprived both of justice and bliss. It is easy to conclude that an unjust and unhappy superhuman being cannot actually be recognized and revered as a god because he bears a closer resemblance to a human tyrant¹⁷. We could even assume that he is a powerful being with certain characteristics and so on, but this does not show that he would be an authoritative model which can legitimately raise a claim to imitation or obedience.

A second reason why Socrates does not take the gods of the city seriously seems to be the fact that, as he maintains, Zeus does not even exist or, to put it more precisely, Zeus does not exist in nature. Here the other aspect of the problem of Socrates comes to the forefront. In this regard, it seems useful to turn to some important pages of *Natural Right and History*, especially the first part of the chapter on *The Origin of the Idea of Natural Right*. We learn from Strauss' account that the discovery of nature is the work of philosophy and that the discovery of nature is possible when the authority of *nomos* is called into question. This means that nature needs to be discovered, and that there is something that hides it. According to Strauss, authoritative decisions hide nature: in plain English, authority hides nature¹⁸.

The philosopher as such is an enemy of authority as such, but this is not a form of political rebellion: it is a necessity in the same way that it is necessary to dig up the *moly* in order to see its white root (cf. Hom. *Od.* X 303-306). The discovery of nature is guided by the distinction between hearsay and seeing with one's own eyes, and the distinction between what is man-made and what is not man-made. Nonetheless, despite the theoretical intention that drives the philosopher, the discovery of nature is never politically innocent. In fact, the discovery of nature implies a break with the authority of ancestral laws, or with the authority of divine law. In other words, the philosopher must reject the gods of the city and refuse to acknowledge as sacred what the city holds to be sacred.

As Strauss writes: "Originally, the questions concerning the first things and the right way are answered before they are raised. They are answered by authority. For authority as the right of human beings to be obeyed is essentially derivative from law, and law is originally nothing other than the way of life of the community"¹⁹. The law answers the questions about the first things even before these questions are actually raised. The law, and especially the positive divine law which is revealed by God or

by the gods, makes it pointless to search for the truth about the first things.

But why is it necessary that the law answer the question regarding the first things with authoritarian decisions? I believe the answer is as follows. Strauss writes: "Man cannot live without having thoughts about the first things, and, it was presumed, he cannot live well without being united with his fellows by identical thoughts about the first things, i.e., without being subject to authoritative decisions concerning the first things: it is the law that claims to make manifest the first things or 'what is'"²⁰. The point is that the multiplicity of *nomoi*, or the multiplicity of ancestral laws that contradict each other, especially on the issues regarding the first things, requires the suspension of judgment. Only a rational demonstration can determine which of the many ancestral laws tells the truth; therefore, from the philosophical perspective, authority as such no longer represents the criterion that guides choice: the discovery of nature leads the philosopher to distinguish between *physis* and *nomos*, and then to recognize the customs and ancestral laws of various peoples as conventions.

In *Socrates and Aristophanes*, the distinction between *physis* and *nomos* is decisive for Strauss' argument (pp. 140, 143). If *nomos* is sheer convention, then *nomos* is not part of those things that exist by nature, nor is it part of what is generated, directly or indirectly, by the first causes. *Nomos*, like all artificial or conventional things, depends directly on man. The greater dignity of natural things, or divine things²¹, as compared to *nomos*, is due to the fact that law presupposes nature, but nature does not presuppose the law: nature is the condition of law. Nature exists in the fullest sense, for nature is eternal, and law appears to be a mere human construct²². Socrates, who as a philosopher takes his bearings from the discovery of nature and the devaluation of what does not exist in nature or by nature, cannot see Zeus anywhere. All those phenomena which are traced back to the activity of Zeus are actually phenomena with natural causes. Rain, lightning and thunder are natural phenomena produced by natural causes. Socrates has to deny the existence of Zeus because there is no record, in his empirical observations, of a superhuman being who speaks, thinks and exerts a will (pp. 19, 21).

4. The political conditions of the contemplative life

At this point, the objection of Aristophanes, as I see it, steps in. As is shown by the behavior of his comic heroes or spokesmen, Aristophanes does not believe that the traditional gods exist in nature; therefore, to this extent, the comic poet agrees with Socrates. Trigaius, the hero of *Peace*, is not afraid of the punishment of Zeus (p. 155); Mnesilochus, Euripides' father-in-law in the *Thesmophoriazusai*, knows that only human authorities can punish him (p. 225); Blepyrus, hero of *Pluto*, or *Wealth*, does not hesitate to challenge the father of the gods in order to restore Pluto's sight (p. 291); Pisthetaerus, the superhuman founder of the *Birds*, dethrones Zeus and obtains his absolute power over gods and men (pp. 163, 188-89). The heroes of Aristophanes behave with full awareness of the weakness of Zeus, who cannot actually punish anyone.

His weakness seems to be the comic equivalent of his nonexistence (p. 143): only men who believe in Zeus can punish other men in the name of Zeus. Zeus has no power to punish anyone, and requires the assistance of man. But what constitutes, then, the difference between Socrates and Aristophanes on the issue of Zeus? Aristophanes would say: “of course, Zeus does not exist in nature, but he exists by convention. And this convention is something you’d better not dismantle so irresponsibly”. Socrates radically devalues convention, or *nomos*, because he looks only at nature. The greater dignity of *physis* compared to *nomos* becomes for the philosopher a greater epistemological and axiological dignity as well, but the perspective of the citizen turns this axiological hierarchy upside down. By not taking the city seriously, Socrates fails to understand the importance of *nomos* and the fundamental role played by the belief in God or in the gods²³.

Aristophanes knows that Zeus does not exist in nature, but he also knows that the actions of men who believe in Zeus have a real impact, for the actions of believers are just as real as those natural phenomena which Socrates observes. Opinions about the gods rule the world of human affairs, not the world of nature, but the world of human affairs is the world to which Socrates is necessarily bound by the simple fact of being a human being, even if he lives as if he were an Epicurean god. The comic poet compels us to reflect on this great misunderstanding on the part of those who lead a philosophic way of life.

The criticism of Aristophanes is not the criticism of someone whom we would define today as a *theocon*. In a remarkable passage, Strauss says that both Socrates and Aristophanes belong to the same species of man, although to two different subspecies (p. 46, cf. p. 17). The poet and the unpolitical philosopher are perfectly and necessarily distinct from one another; nevertheless they seem to share something very important. If we abstract from the specific difference between the poet and the unpolitical philosopher, and even if we abstract from the rivalry between these two forms of wisdom, we can see that in both cases we are dealing with human beings that Strauss would characterize as “nonconformists, people who are prepared to stand alone, to fight alone, ‘rugged individualists’”²⁴. Both the poet and the philosopher stand above and beyond the city (p. 77). Both of them reach a happiness that puts them above the city, an essentially private happiness²⁵, which is not directly determined by the regime and by the laws that govern the world of human affairs.

There is a statement in Nietzsche’s *Birth of Tragedy* that seems to describe exactly the specific difference between poet and philosopher:

Auch der theoretische Mensch hat ein unendliches Genügen am Vorhandenen, wie der Künstler [...] Wenn nämlich der Künstler bei jeder Enthüllung der Wahrheit immer nur mit verzückten Blicken an dem hängen bleibt, was auch jetzt, nach der Enthüllung, noch Hülle bleibt, genießt und befriedigt sich der theoretische Mensch an der abgeworfenen Hülle und hat sein höchstes Lustziel in dem Prozess einer immer glücklichen, durch eigene Kraft gelingenden Enthüllung²⁶.

This statement would fit perfectly in the context of the Straussian comment on the comedies of Aristophanes. A

character like Dikaiopolis shows us the perfect happiness of the comic poet who manages to enjoy himself and his art, thinking only about himself, focusing solely on himself. Seen in this way, he does not seem to be different from the pre-Socratic Socrates, who dedicates himself entirely to the study of divine or natural things, to the contemplative life. Even this Socrates, like the poet, is totally focused on himself and his own happiness.

As Nietzsche maintains in *Morgenröthe*, the philosopher and the poet are two examples of the contemplative life²⁷, for both of them reach a perfect bliss thanks to an unpolitical way of life (p. 74). In this way the poet and the unpolitical philosopher are similar. Thanks to this affinity, the unpolitical philosopher can learn from the poet how to defend himself before the tribunal of the city: is not Dikaiopolis’ apology before the Acharnians indeed the model of any possible defense of a philosopher before the tribunal of the city (pp. 60-67)? The poet, unlike the pre-Socratic philosopher, knows the nature of the city, because he takes his bearings from what is first for us. As becomes clear from Plato’s *Symposium*, where Socrates states that Aristophanes divides his time between Dionysus and Aphrodite (177d7-e3), the comic poet begins with that *alogon* which is the foundation of the family and therefore the foundation of the city (pp. 49, 173). The unpolitical philosopher, blind to the needs of Eros, fails to understand the basic needs of the multitude. Firstly, he remains blind to the desire for beautiful and imperishable superhuman beings (pp. 82-83); secondly, the unpolitical philosopher has no feeling for what is naturally festive and golden, such as the pleasures associated with the rural world of comedy: women, wine, food, laughter, singing and dancing together in the popular festivals in the country (pp. 173, 307). Lastly, the pre-Socratic philosopher cannot understand the negative side of the erotic soul of the multitude. Not without some exaggeration, we might say that patricide and incest are the erotic crimes par excellence. The pre-Socratic philosopher failed to realize the danger he was courting by denying the foundation on which the sacredness of the prohibition of incest and patricide is established. This ignorance makes the pre-Socratic philosopher unable to appreciate the role played by the belief in God or in the gods.

5. A lesson in political prudence

Therefore, only an external constraint can coerce the unpolitical philosopher to involve himself in human affairs, and therefore to cross-examine the most authoritative opinions that govern the world of human affairs:

Philosophy [...] was concerned only negatively, only accidentally, with political things. Socrates himself, the founder of political philosophy, was famous as a philosopher before he ever turned to political philosophy. Left to themselves, the philosophers would not descend again to the “cave” of political life, but would remain outside in what they considered “the island of the blessed” – contemplation of the truth²⁸.

This means that only an external necessity, the clash with some non-philosophical instance, can force the unpolitical

philosopher to reflect on the conditions and the dangers of his philosophical way of life. In this sense, the origin of political philosophy is due to a compulsion to self-knowledge, and thanks to this constraint, the pre-Socratic philosopher understands that the political community, or *nomos*, is the necessary condition of the philosophical way of life, the life according to nature²⁹. But the city is not naturally inclined to philosophy; the city is profoundly indifferent, if not hostile, to philosophy. Aristophanes makes us clearly understand this fact when Pisthetaeus kicks Meton out of the city of the birds (pp. 175, 182). Meton is the character most similar to Socrates. Philosophy is not the “one thing needful” to the city. The city does not gladly bear someone who is, at the same time, useless and dangerous, even less gladly someone who might pose as an Epicurean god, utterly blissful and unconcerned. From the philosophical point of view, the city is primarily a means of survival.

We can therefore plainly state the strictly *political* character of Aristophanes’ lesson. Commonly, Socrates is held to be a champion of *phronesis*, that is, “that kind of knowledge which is inseparable from ‘moral virtue’, i.e. goodness of character or of the habit of choosing, just as moral virtue is inseparable from prudence”³⁰. Can we say the same of the Socrates who has been taught by the comical poet? The Socrates chastened by the clouds does not recant his atheism and his selfishness. We may surmise that he understood the necessity of respecting (at least publicly) piety and justice, and therefore his political wisdom would be but a wary, utilitarian approach to things political, rather than a moral concern for the common good.

In *Birds*, v. 376, we read that the wise learn how to be cautious from the enemy (p. 165). The word in question is not *phronesis* but *eulabeia*; this kind of circumspection recommends that the philosopher deal cautiously with what is sacred to the city. This prudence is a kind of noble fear.³¹ Is this the same kind of circumspection that gives its name to the seal of Spinoza, *caute*?³² Does not the wise Socrates learn how to be cautious from the friendly enemy Aristophanes? The lesson of the comic poet may be summarized by this fundamental rule of thumb: “Don’t separate wisdom from moderation”, where moderation is not a virtue of thought, but of speech³³. In a sense, Aristophanes shows that the philosopher should conceive an exoteric teaching, or a better one³⁴.

It is not possible to determine whether Socrates had personally put this lesson into practice. Certainly, according to Strauss, Xenophon and Plato did as they handed the figure – until now traditional – of the citizen-philosopher Socrates down to history. The idealization of Socrates is the philosophical politics of his disciples (p. 314). Going back to *The Clouds* of Aristophanes, and reopening the quarrel between poetry and philosophy, Strauss makes us understand why political philosophy, understood as political action in defense of philosophy³⁵, has been (and still is) possible and necessary.

Notes

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¹ Cf. D. JANSSENS, *The Philosopher’s Ancient Clothes: Leo Strauss on Philosophy and Poetry*, in P. Armada, A. Gornisiewicz (ed. by), *Modernity and What has been Lost: Considerations on the Legacy of Leo Strauss*, St. Augustine Press, South Bend 2011, pp. 53-71; T. BURNS, *Philosophy and Poetry: A New Look at an Old Quarrel*, in “American Political Science Review”, 109, 2015, pp. 326-338.

² See, for example, M. MARTELLI, *Filosofia e società nel giovane Nietzsche, 1870-1873*, QuattroVenti, Urbino 1983; L. ALFIERI, *Apollo tra gli schiavi: la filosofia sociale e politica di Nietzsche, 1869-1876*, Franco Angeli, Milano 1984; D. LOSURDO, *Nietzsche, il ribelle aristocratico: biografia intellettuale e bilancio critico*, Bollati Boringhieri, Torino 2002; for a Nietzschean interpretation of Strauss (and a Straussian interpretation of Nietzsche as well) see L. LAMPERT, *Leo Strauss and Nietzsche*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1996; L. LAMPERT, *The enduring importance of Leo Strauss*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 2013.

³ Heinrich Meier would speak of a renewal of philosophy *tout court*: cf. H. MEIER, *Politische Philosophie und die Herausforderung der Offenbarungsreligion*, C.H. Beck, München 2013.

⁴ On this puzzling work of Strauss, see C. H. ZUCKERT, *Postmodern Platos: Nietzsche, Heidegger, Gadamer, Strauss, Derrida*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago 1996; L. BIBARD, *La sagesse et le féminin: science, politique et religion selon Kojève et Strauss*, L’Harmattan, Paris 2005; M. STELLA, *The Plaything of Things, ou les Nuées selon Leo Strauss*, in A. Laks, R. Saetta Cottone (ed. by), *Comédie et philosophie: Socrate et les présocratiques dans les «Nuées» d’Aristophane*, Ed. Rue d’Ulm, Paris 2013, pp. 207-223; D. STAUFFER, *Leo Strauss’s Unsocratic Aristophanes?*, in J. Mhire, B. P. Frost (ed. by), *The Political Theory of Aristophanes: Explorations in Poetic Wisdom*, State University of New York Press, Albany 2014, pp. 331-351; M. MENON, *Saggezza politica e poesia. Leo Strauss lettore di Aristofane*, Universitas Studiorum, Mantova 2016.

⁵ L. STRAUSS, *On Tyranny*, ed. by V. Gourevitch and M. S. Roth, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 2000, p. 309.

⁶ All the references to L. STRAUSS, *Socrates and Aristophanes*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1980, are in parentheses.

⁷ On the problem of tradition in Strauss’ thought, see J. GUNNELL, *The Myth of the Tradition*, in “The American Political Science Review”, 72, 1978, pp. 122-134; N. TARCOV, *Philosophy & History: Tradition and Interpretation in the Work of Leo Strauss*, in “Polity”, 16, 1983, pp. 5-29.

⁸ See for example H. ARENDT, *Philosophy and Politics*, in “Social Research”, 57, 1990, pp. 73-103.

⁹ Cf. L. STRAUSS, *The Spirit of Sparta, or the Taste of Xenophon*, in “Social Research”, 6, 1939, pp. 502-536: 532, with F. NIETZSCHE, *Götzen-Dämmerung*, KSA 6, ed. by Giorgio Colli, Mazzino Montinari, De Gruyter, Berlin-New York 1967-77 e 1988, “Das Problem des Sokrates”.

¹⁰ Cf. G. COLLI, *Scritti su Nietzsche*, Adelphi, Milano 1980, p. 40.

¹¹ Cf. L. STRAUSS, *Studies in Platonic Political Philosophy*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1983, p. 175.

¹² A. BLOOM, *The Closing of the American Mind: How Higher Education has Failed Democracy and Impoverished the Souls of Today’s Students*, Simon and Schuster, New York 1987, p. 269.

¹³ Cf. S. SMITH, *Philosophy as a Way of Life: The Case of Leo Strauss*, in “The Review of Politics”, 71, 2009, pp. 37-53.

¹⁴ Cf. L. STRAUSS, *Persecution and the Art of Writing*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1988, p. 14.

¹⁵ The gods of the ancient Greeks are said to be childish, proud tyrants, mortal, powerless, boastful, unjust, and poor (cf. STRAUSS, *Liberalism Ancient and Modern*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1995, p. 103; STRAUSS, *Socrates and Aristophanes*, pp. 33, 143, 155, 188, 288, 294).

¹⁶ Cf. L. STRAUSS, *Farabi’s Plato*, in *Louis Ginzberg Jubilee Volume*, American Academy for Jewish Research, New York 1945, p. 370: “theoretical philosophy by itself, and nothing else, produces the true happiness in this life, i.e., the only happiness which is possible”.

¹⁷ Cf. Arist. *Nic. Eth.* 1178b7-24 with the argument of natural theology, as outlined in L. STRAUSS, *On the Mutual Influence of Theology and Philosophy*, in “The Independent Journal of Philosophy”, 3, 1979, pp. 111-118: 117; L. STRAUSS, *Reason and Revelation*, in H. Meier, *Leo Strauss and the Theologico-Political Problem*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 2006, pp. 141-179: 153-54. See also MEIER, *Politische Philosophie und die Herausforderung der Offenbarungsreligion*, pp. 83-88.

¹⁸ See C. BRUELL, *The Question of Nature and the Thought of Leo Strauss*, in “Klesis – Revue de Philosophie”, 19, 2011, pp. 92-101. The relation between authority and nature seems to sketch out the relation

between revelation and reason: cf. S. SMITH, *Leo Strauss between Athens and Jerusalem*, in "The Review of Politics", 53, 1991, pp. 75-99; H. JAFFA, *Leo Strauss, the Bible, and Political Philosophy*, in K.L. Deutsch, W. Nicgorski (eds.), *Leo Strauss: Political Philosopher and Jewish Thinker*, Rowman and Littlefield, Lanham 1994, pp. 195-201; MEIER, *Leo Strauss and the Theologico-Political Problem*.

¹⁹ L. STRAUSS, *Natural Right and History*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1965, p. 84.

²⁰ STRAUSS, *Natural Right and History*, p. 91.

²¹ Cf. L. STRAUSS, *What is Political Philosophy? And Other Studies*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1988, p. 92.

²² Cf. STRAUSS, *Natural Right and History*, pp. 89-90.

²³ Cf. V. GOUREVITCH, *Philosophy and Politics II*, in "Review of Metaphysics", 22, 1968, pp. 281-328: 297-299.

²⁴ STRAUSS, *What is Political Philosophy?*, p. 38.

²⁵ On the strict similarity between modern liberal thought and the position assumed by Aristophanes, see R. VELKLEY, *Heidegger, Strauss, and the Premises of Philosophy: On Original Forgetting*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 2011, pp. 147-148, 155.

²⁶ F. NIETZSCHE, *Die Geburt der Tragödie*, KSA 1, ed. by G. Colli, M. Montinari, De Gruyter, Berlin-New York 1967-77 and 1988, §15.

²⁷ F. NIETZSCHE, *Morgenröte*, KSA 3, ed. by G. Colli, M. Montinari, De Gruyter, Berlin-New York 1967-77 and 1988, §41.

²⁸ STRAUSS, *What is Political Philosophy?*, p. 92.

²⁹ Cf. N. TARCOV, *Leo Strauss's "On Classical Political Philosophy"*, in R. Major (ed. by), *Leo Strauss's Defense of the Philosophic Life: Reading "What is Political Philosophy?"*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 2013, pp. 65-79.

³⁰ L. STRAUSS, *The City and Man*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 1978, p. 24.

³¹ Cf. STRAUSS, *Natural Right and History*, p. 206.

³² Cf. STRAUSS, *Persecution and the Art of Writing*, p. 180.

³³ Cf. STRAUSS, *What is Political Philosophy?*, p. 32.

³⁴ On the multifaceted meaning of esotericism, and therefore of exotericism, see A. MELZER, *Philosophy Between the Lines: The Lost History of Esoteric Writing*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago-London 2014.

³⁵ See STRAUSS, *What is Political Philosophy?*, p. 126.